

Spectrophotometric determination of vanadium and indium

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Abstract : Extraction of vanadium and indium as their *N*-methylethylxanthocarbamate has been carried out by co-precipitation onto microcrystalline naphthalene. Their spectrophotometric determination has been done in the range 425–435 nm by replacement with copper. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0–40 μg for vanadium and 0–7 μg for indium per 10 ml of the final chloroform solution. The molar absorptivities and sensitivities in the terms of Sandell's definition were calculated to be $1.469 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3.5 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for vanadium and $2.19 \times 10^{-4} \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $5.3 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for indium, respectively. The percentage co-precipitations of vanadium and indium are 99.2 and 98.5 respectively. The method is suitable for preconcentration of these metal ions from a larger volume (~100 ml) of the aqueous phase, and has been employed for their determination in standard reference materials and synthetic samples.

Keywords : Indium, vanadium, spectrophotometric determination.

Introduction

Experimental techniques in order to enhance the selectivity by way of exchange reactions are of great variety and some are very ingenious. Silver may be extracted with a solution of copper diethyldithiocarbamate in ethyl acetate and then the displaced copper in the aqueous phase is polarographed for determining silver in alloys¹. Colourless complexes can also be determined colorimetrically by an indirect method, e.g. the cadmium diethyldithiocarbamate may be shaken with aqueous solution of copper sulphate and the determination was made for the exchanged copper diethyldithiocarbamate in organic phase². Kamstu and Kowano³ determined mercury by displacing copper from copper diethyldithiocarbamate solution based on the fact that the decrease in absorption due to copper diethyldithiocarbamate at 440 nm is proportional to the amount of mercury in aqueous phase.

The capacity of an element to enter the exchange reaction may be estimated in a series sequence of elements, which has been established empirically. One such series representing the behavior of metal ions extracted as their diethyldithiocarbamate from solution at pH 8.5–11.0 was established by Gottschalk⁴. Bankovskil and coworkers⁵ established a similar series for 8-mercaptoquinolates. Bode^{6,7} and Eckert⁸ studied the exchange reactions of diethyldithiocarbamate. Other extractable chelate com-

pounds, which were subjected to exchange reactions, include substituted thiophosphates and dithiophosphates⁹, morpholine-4-carbodithioates¹⁰, xanthates¹¹, etc.

In the present section, conditions have been developed for the extraction of vanadium and indium as their *N*-methylethylxanthocarbamate by co-precipitation onto microcrystalline naphthalene. These metal complexes absorb weakly, and their determination is thus carried out by replacement with copper which absorbs strongly in the range 425–435 nm with $\epsilon = 1.476 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The method has been applied to the determination of these metals in certain complex materials.

Experimental

Reagents : The entire reagents used were of analytical grade. Solution of ammonium metavanadate and indium sulphate (each of 10^{-2} M) were prepared in distilled water from their analytical grade reagent samples and standardized by the known method¹². The 0.2% solution of the present (potassium *N*-methylethylxanthocarbamate)¹³ was prepared by dissolving the required solid mass in 2 ml of dimethyl formamides, and then diluted with distilled water. A 20% naphthalene solution was prepared in acetone. Buffer solution were prepared from 1 *M* acetic acid and 1 *M* ammonium acetate for pH 3–6, and 1 *M* aqueous ammonia and 1 *M* ammonium acetate for pH 8–

11. Dilute solutions of perchloric acid and ammonia were used for pH adjustments.

Apparatus : An Elico pH meter and Pye Unicam sp-500/sp-700 recording spectrometers were used.

General procedure : To an aliquot of each metal ion solution taken in a stoppered Erlenmeyer flask was added 2 ml of the reagent solution (0.2%) and 5 ml of acetic-acetate buffer of pH 4.0 for vanadium and 6.0 for indium. The solution was diluted to about 30 ml with distilled water. The content of the flask was shaken thoroughly and then allowed to stand for about 2 min. It was again shaken vigorously while adding 2 ml of 20% naphthalene solution in fast stream. The solid mass was filtered off on a Whatman filter paper (no. 1042), washed 2–3 times with distilled water, drained dry, dissolved in chloroform and diluted to 10 ml in a standard flask. The whole solution was then transferred to a separatory funnel. 10 ml of 10^{-3} M copper nitrate solution was added to it in order to develop a yellow colour in the chloroform layer. These solutions were shaken vigorously for about 5 min and then the chloroform layer was pored on to anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g) taken in a beaker in order to remove the last traces of water. A portion of this solution was taken in a 1 cm glass cell and the absorbance was measured at 430 nm against the reagent blank in each case.

Results and discussion

Preliminary observations have revealed that neither the reagent nor the metal ions are co-precipitated with microcrystalline naphthalene when taken individually. It was also found that copper forms a very stable complex with *N*-methylethylxanthocarbamate. Since xanthates are analogous to dithiocarbamates, naturally the copper *N*-methylethylxanthocarbamate will be more stable than the vanadium and indium *N*-methylethylxanthocarbamate. Thus, copper according to the equations given below will replace these metals :

Although a stoichiometric amount of copper could be used for quantitative replacement of these metals, but for safe

side, 10 ml of 10^{-3} M copper sulphate solution was used in all the cases. It has been reported that copper *N*-methylethylxanthocarbamate in chloroform solution absorbs strongly in the range 425–435 nm with $\epsilon = 1.476 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Thus in all cases, absorbance was measured at 430 nm against the reagent blank in each case.

Effect of pH : Co-precipitations were carried out by the general procedure at different pH keeping other conditions constant. The absorbances remained unaltered in the pH range 1.5–6.3 for vanadium and 4.5–8.0 for indium. Addition of more than 3 ml of the buffer solutions pH 4.0 for vanadium and 6.0 for indium were required for quantitative co-precipitations from a 30 ml aqueous phase. Therefore, 5 ml of each buffer solution was subsequent studies.

Effect of reagent concentration :

At optimum conditions co-precipitations were quantitative when slightly more than stoichiometric amounts of reagents solution were used. However, for a safe side, 2 ml of 0.2% reagent solution were used in all the cases.

Effect of naphthalene : The co-precipitations were found to be quantitative when more the 0.5 ml 20% naphthalene solutions were used. However, 2 ml of the naphthalene solution was preferred for subsequent studies.

Effect of digestion time and shaking times :

The effect of digestion time on the absorption was investigated by digesting these metal complexes for 1–30 min before the co-precipitations were carried out. It was found that the absorbance remained constant in all the cases for a period of 2–30 min of digestion time was chosen for subsequent studies.

The effect of shaking time on the co-precipitation of these metal complexes was also studied. The rate of co-precipitations of these metals complexes on to micro-crystalline naphthalene was very fast and on change in the degree of co-precipitation was observed during the shaking period of 1–5 min.

Effect of aqueous phase volume :

Under the experiment conditions described above, the co-precipitations were found to be quantitative when total volume of the aqueous phase was not more than 100 ml in both the cases.

Beer's law and sensitivity :

Under the optimum described above, calibration graphs were constructed at 430 nm in both the cases. Beer's law holds in the concentration ranges 0.0–40.0 µg for vanadium and 0.0–70.0 µg for indium per 10 ml of the final solution. The concentration ranges which Ringbom plots are 0.6–3.0 ppm for vanadium and 0.8–5.0 ppm for indium can determine accurately. The molar absorptivities and sensitivities in terms of Sandell's definition were calculated to be $1.469 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ µg cm}^{-2}$ for vanadium and $2.187 \times 10^{-4} \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $5.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ µg cm}^{-2}$ for indium, respectively. Aliquots containing 15.6 µg vanadium and 29.4 µg indium gave mean absorbance of 0.450 and 0.560 with relative standard deviations $\pm 0.57\%$ and $\pm 0.45\%$, respectively. The percentage co-precipitation was established in each case by back extracting the metal from chloroform layer with 20 ml of 3 M nitric acid before the replacement with copper. Each of the metal was then determined spectrophotometrically or polarographically. The co-precipitations were found to be 99.2% for vanadium (theoretical values are 99.53% for vanadium and 98.78% for indium by comparing the molar absorptivities with that of copper).

Composition of metal xanthates :

Under the optimum conditions, the composition of vanadium and indium *N*-methylethylxanthocarbamate was established by Job's method of continuous variation. Peaks at 0.32 mole fraction for vanadium and 0.23 for indium suggested the formation of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 (metal : ligand) complexes. Further, these compositions were ascertained by the logarithmic method¹⁴. The required values of $\log [MR_n]/[M^{n+}]$ and $\log [HR]$ for the method were calculated and plotted. Straight lines with slopes equal to 1.76 for vanadium and 2.82 for indium were obtained which suggested the formation of $\text{VO}[\text{CH}_3\text{CH}(\text{OCS})\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)\text{CS}_2]_2$ and $\text{In}[\text{CH}_3\text{CH}(\text{OCS})\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)\text{CS}_2]_3$ as reported in the literature for usual xanthates¹⁵.

Effect of diverse ions :

In general, for the interference studies, 100 mg salt of anions or 500 µg of the metal ions were added individually to aliquots containing 15.6 µg of vanadium and 29.4 µg of indium. Among the anions examined (Table 1) most

Table 1. Effect of diverse anions

Salts of the anions added	Amount added	Absorbance of 430 nm	
		Vanadium	Indium
-	-	0.450	0.560
Sodium fluoride	100	0.448	0.554
Potassium chloride	100	0.450	0.560
Potassium bromide	100	0.446	0.560
Potassium iodide	100	0.448	0.556
Tri-sodium phosphate	100	0.445	0.558
Sodium carbonate	100	0.450	0.555
Potassium sulphate	100	0.450	0.560
Sodium nitrate	100	0.450	0.560
Potassium thiosulphate	100	0.450	0.560
Sodium acetate	100	0.450	0.560
Sodium oxalate	100	0.430	0.525
-	30	0.446	0.553
Sodium citrate	100	0.445	0.557
Ammonium titrate	100	0.450	0.556
Di-sodium EDTA	100	0.450	0.560

Conditions : V : 15.6 g; pH : 4.0; In : 29.4 g; pH : 6.0; 0.2% reagent solution : 2 ml in each case; 20% naphthalene solution : 2 ml in each case.

of them did not interfere in both the cases except oxalate. However, a relatively low amount of it could be tolerated. Among the cations examined (Table 2), Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Fe^{III} , Pb^{II} , Pd^{II} and Zn^{II} interfered in both the cases. The interference of all these metal ions except Fe^{III} and Pb^{II} was eliminated by masking with 5 ml of 10% sodium cyanide while that of iron and lead was masked with 5 ml of 10% EDTA. The determination of indium in the pres-

Table 2. Effect of diverse cations

Metal salt added	Metal ion added	Absorbance of 430 nm	
		Vanadium	Indium
-	-	0.450	0.560
Aluminum nitrate	2000	0.450	0.560
Ammonium metavanadate(v)	200	-	0.605 ^a
-	100	-	0.566 ^a
Ammonium molybdate	500	0.453 ^c	0.566
Antimony(III) chloride	500	0.450 ^b	0.565
Bismuth nitrate	500	0.448	0.562
Cadmium chloride	500	0.450	0.568
Chromium(III) nitrate	1000	0.450	0.560
Cobalt(II) nitrate	500	0.452 ^d	0.566 ^d
Copper(II) chloride	500	0.454 ^d	0.567 ^d
Indium sulphate	500	0.450 ^b	-

Table-2 (contd.)

Iridium(III) chloride	500	0.450	0.564
Iron(III) chloride	500	0.453 ^e	0.566 ^e
Lead(III) nitrate	500	0.455 ^e	0.563 ^e
Manganese(II) acetate	500	0.450	0.560
Mercuric(II) chloride	300	0.428	0.536
-	100	0.443	0.554
Nickel chloride	500	0.456 ^d	0.567 ^d
Niobium pentaoxide	500	0.450	0.560
Osmium(VIII) tetraoxide	500	0.450	0.560
Palladium(II) chloride	200	0.620	0.630
-	-	0.453 ^d	0.568
Platinum(IV) chloride	500	0.445	0.560
Potassium(II) selenite	500	0.450	0.560
Rhodium(II) chloride	200	0.453	0.566
Ruthenium(II) chloride	200	0.454	0.565
Silver(I) nitrate(V)	500	0.450	0.560
Sodium arsenite(III)	500	0.450	0.560
Thallos nitrate	500	0.450	0.565
Thorium(IV) nitrate	500	0.450	0.565
Sodium tungstate(VI)	500	0.450	0.560
Uranyl acetate(VI)	500	0.450	0.560
Zinc nitrate	200	0.456 ^d	0.562 ^d
Zirconyl(II) chloride	500	0.450	0.560

^aIridium was determined at pH 8.0; ^bVanadium was determined at pH 1.5 in the presence of antimony of iridium; ^cAfter co-precipitating out molybdenum complex from 2 M perchloric acid media; ^dAfter masking with 5 ml of 10% sodium cyanide; ^eAfter masking with 5 ml of 10% EDTA solution.

Conditions : Same as in Table 1.

ence of vanadium was carried out at pH 8.0. Similarly, vanadium in the presence of antimony and indium was determined at pH 1.5.

Determination of vanadium in standard reference materials :

A 1–2 g amount of the standard reference samples of the alloys was completely dissolved in 20–40 ml of hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) on a boiling water bath, and then 3–5 ml of 30% hydrogen peroxide was added. The excess of hydrogen peroxide was decomposed on heating the sample solution on the water bath. It was cooled and filtered through a filter paper. The filtrate was diluted to 100 ml with distilled water in a standard flask. To an aliquot of the sample solutions 5 ml of 10% sodium cyanide were added in order to mask Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and 5 ml of 10% EDTA to mask Fe^{III} and Pb^{II}. High amounts of iron present in steel samples were pre-extracted with acetylacetone at pH 8.0 then; from the aqueous phase vanadium was determined by general procedure. The results are given in Table 3.

Determination of vanadium in synthetic environmental samples :

A synthetic sample solution related to fertilizer industry waste water containing various cations and anions was prepared and the determination of vanadium was carried out by the general procedure. The results are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Determination of vanadium in standard reference materials

Sample	Composition (%)	Amount of vanadium (µg)		Average (µg)	Relative standard deviation (%)
		Taken	Found		
NKK, 920	V : 0.15, Co : 0.10	22.6	22.87	22.64	±0.80
Aluminum	Fe : 0.72, Ti : 0.15		22.38		
	Mg : 0.46, Si : 0.78		22.66		
	Ca : 0.03, Cu : 0.71		22.57		
	Ni : 0.29, Zn : 0.80		22.72		
	Sb : 0.01, Cr : 0.27				
JSS, 174-3	V : 0.0063	25.0	25.35	25.07	±0.88
Carbon steel alloy	Co : 0.02		24.88		
	Nb : 0.02		25.07		
	Zr : 0.024		24.83		
	B : 0.00053		25.21		

	Sb : 0.00099				
	Al : 0.03				
	C : 0.044				
JSS, 513-4	V : 0.05, Cu : 0.074	27.7	28.14	27.76	±1.05
Chromium	Mo : 0.01, Ni : 0.130		27.58		
steel alloy	Cr : 1.05, Al : 0.250		27.91		
	Mn : 0.79, Si : 0.250		27.76		
	S : 0.01, P : 0.012		27.39		
	C : 0.16, N : 0.012				
Synthetic	V : 0.2, As : 0.40	20.0	20.45	20.23	±0.68
environmental	Cr ^{VI} : 0.04				
sample related	Cr ^{III} : 4.00				
to fertilizer	NO ₃ : 20.00, CN : 0.40				
industry	PO ₄ : 5.00, F : 10.00				

Table 4. Determination of indium in synthetic samples

Amount of foreign ion present (mg)	Amount of vanadium (µg)		Average (µg)	Relative standard deviation (%)
	Taken	Found		
Bi : 0.100, Ti : 0.100	34.2	34.56	34.26	±0.68
Zn : 0.200, As : 0.400		34.18		
Mn : 0.300, Sb : 0.100		33.93		
		34.36		
		34.29		
Cd : 0.100, Pb : 0.100	46.0	46.34	46.08	±0.56
Pb : 0.200, Fe : 0.100		46.19		
Mo : 0.100, W : 0.500		45.72		
		46.25		
		45.91		
Al : 0.500, Co : 0.100	39.5	39.15	39.49	±0.70
Ni : 0.00, Sn : 0.500		39.65		
Cr : 0.500, Cu : 0.100		39.42		
		39.87		
		39.38		
Pb : 0.100, Mg : 0.500	45.9	46.13	45.98	
Al : 0.500, Fe : 0.100		46.02		±0.50
Hg : 0.100, Zn : 0.100		46.65		
		46.24		
		45.87		

Determination of indium in synthetic samples :

Solutions of different synthetic sample were prepared by dissolving the foreign metal salts along with that of indium in distilled water. To an aliquot of each solution was added 5 ml of 10% sodium cyanide, and the general procedure was then followed. The results are given in Table 4.

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